

THE ROLE OF WORK STRESS AND JOB SATISFACTION IN THE MEDIATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE TO ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the direct and indirect effect of organizational culture on organizational commitment through job stress and job satisfaction. This study uses quantitative analysis with a total sample of 231 Prima University lecturers determined by using random sampling. The data analysis used is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. The results of the study indicate that organizational culture has a positive and significant direct effect on job satisfaction and job stress. Then job satisfaction and job stress have a direct positive effect on organizational commitment. Indirectly, the variables of job stress and job satisfaction can mediate organizational culture on organizational commitment.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Job Stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Private universities as part of the national education system need to be continuously encouraged to seek to strengthen the ability of their academic community to become more professional and of high quality. Higher education success is determined by accountability and the ability to carry out the duties of the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. The Tri Dharma of Higher Education includes teaching, research, and community service. Anggraeni (2013) revealed that lecturers are required to carry out the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, in which research activities are followed up with the publication of scientific papers that are carried out internally and externally to improve the performance of lecturers. However, carrying out this requires competent and highly committed lecturers so that the desired goals and objectives are achieved. The issue of lecturer commitment in higher education has attracted the attention of the public, educators, and other stakeholders in the field of education. Based on observations of the phenomenon of lecturer competence, it was found that the knowledge of the lecturers about the subjects being taught was still low and was judged not to be by the orientation of quality, problem-solving skills, skills, planning, teamwork, and independent learning capacity. As a result, low competence causes job dissatisfaction, low organizational commitment of lecturers, and decreased performance. The same thing can also be seen in that the job satisfaction of lecturers in teaching has not been as expected. Many lecturers complain about the low remuneration in the form of compensation for the career positions occupied, not getting improved working conditions as expected to support their careers, rarely getting promotions

according to functional ranks and positions, and organizational culture that is less supportive because of its nature that tends to be top-down, and the absence of opportunities to develop themselves in the field of higher education. In connection with the above, it is necessary to conduct an assessment of organizational commitment. In general, organizational commitment is an employee's attachment to the organization where the employee works. According to Allen and Meyer (1997), there are three components of organizational commitment, namely affective commitment, rational commitment, and normative commitment. According to Meyer, (2002) and Yousef, (2000) stated that employee commitment to the organization is a factor that must be owned by every member of the organization because commitment to the organization is believed to be a driving force for employees to be serious in working so that they can meet the work targets given to them. . Ahmad (2015) stated that every lecturer's dissatisfaction can reduce their level of commitment to the institution.

According to Hadjimichael and Haridimos, (2019) empirically, several factors have been shown to influence employee organizational commitment in this case the lecturer profession. Many theories examine a person's commitment, one of which is the theory put forward by Colquitt, LePine, and Wesson (2015: 9) which states that several factors influence a person's commitment, including factors that directly determine include: job satisfaction (job satisfaction), emphasis (stress), motivation (motivation), trust, justice, and ethics (trust, justice, and ethics), and learning and decision-making (learning & decision making). Meanwhile, indirect factors include organizational factors (organizational culture, organizational structure), group factors (leadership style and behavior, leadership strength and influence, team processes, and team characteristics), and individual characteristics (cultural and personality values, abilities). Based on the theory of Colquitt, LePine, and Wesson above, organizational mechanisms, team mechanisms, and individual characteristics build individual mechanisms to foster commitment, in other words, the formation of commitment depends on individual mechanisms that are influenced by organizational mechanisms, team mechanisms, and individual characteristics. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that two major factors influence organizational commitment, namely personal factors and environmental factors. Personal factors include job satisfaction and job stress. From environmental factors, the researcher argues that organizational culture has a direct influence on the organizational commitment of Universitas Prima Indonesia lecturers.

Research results Brief (1998); Navarrese et al (2014); Nasrudin, et al (2004) showed that organizational culture affects the increase in employee job stress in the organization. The results of research by Lolowang, et al (2019); Nwakoby, et al (2018); Qazi, et al (2017); Xiaoming and Hu (2012); Ismail (2015) shows that organizational culture affects the job satisfaction of every employee in the organization. If the organizational culture goes well, every employee will feel satisfaction working in the organization, and vice versa. Bakotic Research (2016); Yucel and Cetin (2012); Zin (2004); Rifai (2005) show that job satisfaction affects organizational commitment. Nayir's research (2012); Greve, et al (2010) show that work motivation affects organizational commitment. Research by Kelly and Phyllis (2007) shows that job stress can significantly affect organizational commitment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SUBMISSION OF HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Lecturer Commitment

According to Colquitt, LePine, and Wesson (2015:67) stated organizational commitment is defined as a desire on the part of an employee to remain a member of the organization. Luthans (2016: 249) suggests organizational commitment can be defined as (1) a strong desire to remain as a member of a particular organization; (2) the desire to strive by the wishes of the organization and (3) certain beliefs and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization. Furthermore, Purba (2010:72) suggests that organizational commitment is a manifestation of a person's willingness in the form of a promise or attachment to the organization, which is described by the amount of effort (energy, time, and thought) used to achieve organizational goals. Thus, a lecturer who has a strong commitment to the organization he leads will want to remain a member of the organization, strive to be by the wishes of the school where he works, and accept the values and goals of the school.

2.2 Organizational Culture

According to Nimran (2016:11), organizational culture is a system of meaning shared by an organization that distinguishes it from other organizations. Meanwhile, according to Griffin and Ebbert (2012), organizational culture can be defined as shared experiences, history, beliefs, and norms that characterize a company/organization. A similar definition is expressed by Moorhead and Griffin (2012) that organizational culture is a set of values that are accepted always right, which helps someone in the organization to understand which actions are acceptable and which actions are not acceptable and these values are communicated through stories and other symbolic means.

2.3 Job Satisfaction

Robbins and Timothy (2015:79) suggest that "Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics". Meanwhile, Luthans (2015: 243) defines it as the result of an individual's perception of his work which can be understood in the dimensions: (1) emotional response to work situations ; (2) dependence on outcome congruence with expectations, and (3) its association with various interrelated attitudes toward work. Furthermore, Mangkunegara (2015: 75) states that job satisfaction is a feeling related to work that involves aspects such as wages or salaries received, career development opportunities, relationships with other workers, job placement, type of work, company organizational structure, quality of supervision, age, health condition, ability, and education.

2.4 Work Stress

Ivancevich, Donnelly, and Gibson (2017) define job stress as an adaptive response, mediated by individual differences and/or psychological processes, which is a consequence of any activity (environment), situation, or external event that imposes psychological or physical demands on it. Too much for someone. Meanwhile, Beehr and Newman in Luthans (2016) define job stress is a condition that arises from the interaction between humans and work and is characterized by human changes that force them to deviate from their normal functions. A

different definition put forward by Robbins (2017), is that stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand that is associated with what he wants and the result is perceived as uncertain and important.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2.5 Research Hypothesis

1. Organizational culture has a direct positive effect on lecturer job satisfaction at Universitas Prima Indonesia
2. Organizational culture has a direct positive effect on work stress at Universitas Prima Indonesia
3. Job satisfaction has a direct positive effect on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia
4. Job stress has a direct negative effect on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia
5. Organizational culture has a positive indirect effect on organizational commitment through lecturer job satisfaction as a mediator at Universitas Prima Indonesia.
6. Organizational culture has a positive indirect effect on organizational commitment through work stress as mediation at Universitas Prima Indonesia.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach. Data were obtained from the distribution of questionnaires with a Likert scale with a total sample of 231 respondents. The research data were analyzed using structural equation model (SEM) analysis based on partial least squares (PLS) which aims to examine the direct and indirect effects of the research variables used.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

Figure 1: Research Variable Loading Factor Value

Based on Figure 2, shows that all variables have met the validity requirements with the loading factor value of all indicators > 0.7. Then the next test can be done.

Construct Reliability Test

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct Reliability and Validity

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Budaya Organisasi	0.946	0.951	0.958	0.822
Kepuasan Kerja	0.906	0.908	0.941	0.842
Komitmen Organisasi	0.941	0.941	0.962	0.894
Stres Kerja	0.865	0.866	0.918	0.788

The results of the analysis shown in Table 1 below show that the AVE value of each latent variable has a value > 0.5 and the value of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha value of each latent variable is more than 0.7, so it can be concluded that the variable indicator can measure well.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 2: R-Square

R Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square A...
Kepuasan Kerja	0.092	0.088
Komitmen Organisasi	0.482	0.477
Stres Kerja	0.188	0.185

Based on Table 2 above, it is found that the R-Square adjusted value of the job satisfaction variable is 0.088 or 8.8% and the remaining 91.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. The work stress variable R-Square adjusted value is 0.185 or 18.5% and the remaining 81.5% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Finally, for the organizational commitment variable, the adjusted R-Square value is 0.477 or 47.7% and the remaining 52.3% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3: Direct Effect

Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Budaya Organisasi -> Kepuasan Kerja	0.303	0.310	0.057	5.274	0.000
Budaya Organisasi -> Stres Kerja	0.434	0.436	0.058	7.454	0.000
Kepuasan Kerja -> Komitmen Organisasi	0.292	0.293	0.056	5.175	0.000
Stres Kerja -> Komitmen Organisasi	0.509	0.508	0.058	8.787	0.000

1. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction

The research results obtained also support the research conducted by Qazi, Mohammad, and Pretty (2017: 215); Ismail (2015:139); Alvi, et al (2014:2), and Rifai (2005:131) that organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Based on hypothesis testing with a path coefficient of $p_{21} = 0.297$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.5$. The results showed that organizational culture affects the job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Prima Indonesia. Theoretically, organizational culture still has to be improved and can be optimized by increasing the indicators of innovation and risk-taking without overriding other indicators as a constituent of organizational culture variables in this study, such as result orientation, people orientation, team orientation, and stability. The results showed that all of the constituent indicators became an important part of increasing organizational culture variables to support the realization of good job satisfaction.

2. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Work Stress

The results obtained also support research conducted by Nwakoby, Jane, and Chika (2018:1213) and Navarrese, Charlene, and Kathy (2014:439) that organizational culture has a significant effect on work stress. Based on hypothesis testing with a path coefficient of $p_{31} = 0.431$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.5$. The results showed that organizational culture affects the work stress of lecturers at Universitas Prima Indonesia. Theoretically, organizational culture still has to be improved and can be optimized by increasing the indicators of innovation and risk-taking without overriding other indicators as a constituent of organizational culture variables in this study, such as result orientation, people orientation, team orientation, and stability. The results showed that all of the constituent indicators became an important part of increasing organizational culture variables to support the realization of good work stress.

3. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment

The research results obtained also support the research conducted by Bakotić (2016: 118); Ismail (2015:139); Alvi, et al (2014:1); Yucel and Cetin (2012:1598), and Rifai (2005:131) that job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment. Based on hypothesis testing with path coefficient $p_{y2} = 0.158$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.001 < 0.5$. The results showed that job satisfaction affects the organizational commitment of lecturers at the University of Prima Indonesia. Theoretically, job satisfaction still has to be improved and can be optimized by increasing the indicators of co-workers' satisfaction without overriding other indicators as constituents of job satisfaction variables in this study, such as promotion satisfaction and supervisory satisfaction.

4. The Effect of Job Stress on Organizational Commitment

The results obtained also support the research conducted by Kelly and Phyllis (2007:487); Nasrudin, Ramayah, and Kumaresan (2004:251) and Brief (1998:193) that work stress have a significant effect on organizational commitment. Based on hypothesis testing with a large path coefficient $p_{y3} = 0.289$ with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.5$. The results showed that work stress affects the organizational commitment of lecturers at the University of Prima Indonesia. In theory, work stress still has to be increased and can be optimized by increasing indicators of unbalanced supervision and training without ruling out other indicators as constituents of work stress variables in this study, such as excessive workload and poor social support.

Table 4. Indirect Effect

	Specific Indirect Effects
Organizational culture -> job satisfaction -> organizational commitment	0.047
Organizational culture -> work stress -> organizational commitment	0.124

5. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment through Lecturer Job Satisfaction

The indirect effect of organizational culture (X1) on organizational commitment (Y) through job satisfaction (X2) is 0.047 or 4.7%. This means that the smallest contribution to organizational culture (X1) in increasing organizational commitment (Y) is given job satisfaction of 4.7%. The results of the study are the results of research conducted by Heriyanti and Zayanti (2021) who found that job satisfaction was able to mediate organizational culture on organizational commitment. Likewise, the results of research conducted by Wibawa and Putra (2018) found that job satisfaction was able to mediate organizational culture on organizational commitment.

6. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Commitment through Work Stress

The indirect effect of organizational culture (X1) on organizational commitment (Y) through work stress (X3) is 0.124 or 12.4%. So it can be concluded that the work stress variable (X3) contributes to organizational culture (X1) in increasing organizational commitment (Y) which is 12.4%. The results of the study are by the statements put forward by Dwilingga (2017) and Satriani et al . (2017) when the culture of an organization is getting stronger, it will further reduce employee work stress which affects, they will tend to highly committed to the organization where they work.

5. CONCLUSION

This research concludes that the organizational culture variable has a direct positive effect on the job satisfaction of lecturers at Universitas Prima Indonesia. Next, the organizational culture variable also has a direct positive effect on the work stress of lecturers at Universitas Prima Indonesia. The job satisfaction variable has a direct positive effect on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia. Likewise, the work stress variable also has a direct positive effect on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia. Meanwhile, indirectly, the job satisfaction variable can mediate organizational culture on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia. Finally, indirectly, the work stress variable is also able to mediate organizational culture on organizational commitment at Universitas Prima Indonesia.

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